

SURVIVING DESPITE INTENTIONAL FOOD & WATER SCARCITY – CASES OF RESILIENCE FROM GAZA (2023-2024)

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ABSTRACT

This paper comprehensively examines the humanitarian crisis in Gaza following the onset of hostilities on October 7, 2023. It focuses on the intentional scarcity of food and water as a warfare tactic. The authors explore how these conditions exacerbate daily life challenges, particularly for vulnerable populations, including children and families.

Through a series of case studies, the research highlights Gazans' remarkable resilience and adaptability, showcasing various initiatives that emerge in response to severe resource constraints in food and water. These initiatives illustrate community solidarity, innovative problem-solving, and the determination to foster hope amidst adversity. This study not only documents the sustained efforts of individuals and groups striving for survival but also calls attention to the urgent need for humanitarian support and systemic change to alleviate the dire circumstances in Gaza. By analysing the interplay between resilience and systematic deprivation, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the ongoing struggle for survival in one of the world's most challenging humanitarian contexts.

Keywords: Gaza, Resilience, Food, Water, Genocide, Food and Water During Wars

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1. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing conflict in Gaza has precipitated a humanitarian crisis characterised by intentional and systematic scarcity of essential resources, particularly food and water. Since October 7, 2023, when hostilities escalated dramatically, the situation has been exacerbated by tactics that prioritise the deprivation of basic necessities as a means of warfare. The literature review thus aims to shed light on the multifaceted challenges currently faced by Gazans while highlighting their remarkable resilience in the face of adversity. Buheji (2024b)

Reports indicate that the conditions of intentional deprivation—used as a weapon by occupying forces—have led to an increased psychological and material burden on the population. Children and families in Gaza are disproportionately affected, enduring violence and loss of hope for the future, which some assert is a calculated initiative to accelerate the erasure of Indigenous Palestinian identities. In a climate of warfare that restricts access to essential goods, Gazans persist in finding ingenious ways to survive daily life, motivated not only by necessity but by an enduring spirit of community and cooperation. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023a)

Therefore, this paper will explore various case studies that exemplify some of the resilience shown by individuals and groups within Gaza in relevance to the area of food and water. The initiatives undertaken underscore the themes of solidarity, resourcefulness, and innovation as Gazans navigate the harsh realities brought on by intentional scarcities. In examining these instances of resilience, the paper will contribute to a broader understanding of the human capacity to adapt and survive under extreme conditions, while also calling for recognition of the ongoing hardships faced by the population and a commitment to addressing the underlying causes of their suffering.

This situation in Gaza regarding food and water scarcity, has drawn significant global attention and concern. Some residents engage in small-scale farming and gardening, utilising available land and resources to grow food, which can help alleviate shortages. Many individuals adapt their diets based on what is available, incorporating alternative food sources and innovative cooking methods requiring less water. In the meanwhile, mental health plays a significant role in survival; community gatherings and cultural practices help maintain a sense of normalcy and hope. Local and international advocates raise awareness about the humanitarian situation, calling for policy changes and support, which contributes to more significant efforts for long-term solutions. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023a)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Brief Situation of Gaza as of December 2024

Food and survival aid in the war on Gaza that started on October 7th, 2023, was always insufficient and intentionally reduced with time as Israelis used it as a weaponisation strategy for water, food, and life essentials. Growing reports from Palestinians in Gaza, and even now in the West Bank, repeating the accusation to Israel of killing and targeting families and especially children to destroy the hope of future generations and to accelerate the ethnic cleansing of the Indigenous Palestinian nations, especially in Gaza.

This puts everyone in Gaza in life challenges every day, including life-threatening situations, to provide their basic needs, starting with water, food, and shelter. All are becoming scarce and require effort and time to find some, if possible. This paper analyses case studies of Gazans' resilience by focusing on the intentional, sustained scarcity of food and water in Gaza that has been planned for a long time.

2.2 Previous Learning from Community Resilience Regarding Food and Water Scarcity from Other Wars

In several published papers, the authors mentioned the importance of learning and innovation in resilient practices. Various initiatives have emerged in response to severe food and water resource constraints, particularly in crisis situations like that in Gaza. For example, part of the resilience in this area is that community kitchens usually prepare and distribute meals to those in need. These kitchens often rely on donations and the involvement of community members to function, providing essential food to vulnerable populations.

Regardless of displacement, citizens would try to convert small patches of land into urban gardens to grow vegetables and fruits. These projects provide fresh produce and promote self-sufficiency and community engagement. Innovative methods for purifying water, such as filtration systems using sand, charcoal, and gravel, can help the community to ensure access to safe drinking water.

In different conflict situations, part of the resilience would be establishing community seed banks where locals can donate and exchange seeds. This initiative encourages the cultivation of diverse crops and fosters agricultural resilience. Collaborations between NGOs and the local community can help create networks to collect surplus food from markets and distribute it to those facing food insecurity, minimising waste while addressing hunger. Buheji (2024b)

Educating families on nutrition and how to source and provide essential supplements to children and vulnerable populations to combat malnutrition amidst food scarcity is also part of agile resilience practices. In coastal areas, similar to Gaza, communities may develop sustainable fishing or small-scale aquaculture initiatives to enhance food security and provide income despite restrictions on fishing zones. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023b).

Rainwater harvesting systems should also be implemented where possible. This would help collect and store rainwater for agricultural and domestic use. Even farmers can innovate by banding together to share resources, equipment, and labour, enhancing their capacity to grow food despite limited access to land and inputs.

In some wars and conflict zones, many initiatives can come to provide training on cooking with limited ingredients, food preservation techniques, and sustainable agricultural practices to empower individuals with skills to make the most of available resources. Community workshops focus on repairing and repurposing items, including kitchenware and farming tools, to reduce waste and decrease dependence on new supplies. These programs include mobile clinics and mental health support, recognising the holistic needs of communities dealing with both physical and emotional challenges related to scarcity. Individuals and community groups use social media and local events to raise funds for purchasing food and water supplies, directly supporting those in need.

Young people also can play an important role during conflicts by organising projects to support their communities, such as community outreach programs that assist in food distribution, awareness campaigns, and recreational activities aimed at fostering a sense of hope and resilience. These initiatives demonstrate the creativity, resourcefulness, and solidarity of communities facing severe resource constraints, highlighting local action's importance in effectively addressing crises. The Guardian (2024).

3. METHODOLOGY

Following the daily videos and news from Gaza for the last thirteen months since October 2023, showing Palestinian citizens' reactions to death, attacks, illness, displacement, occupation, intimidation, loss of loved ones, scarcity of essentials, injuries and disability, the following case studies are chosen to illustrate Palestinians intentional survival despite food and water scarcity. It is essential to state that we found dozens of initiatives worthy of mentioning and analysis, and it is only due to the limitation of what can be included in one paper we were not able to include them all, although they are not less important than the ones studied below.

4. CASE STUDIES

4.1 Takeya System and its Evolution of Gazan's Community Kitchens during the War

4.1.1 Background

Tekeya is a system of community solidarity charity kitchens, warehouses and shops for food making and supplying for charity to everyone in need. The system is more like an ambulance that saves the lives of the wounded till they arrive at the hospital to receive the proper treatment, as described by a Palestinian running a Tekeya (The National, 2024). However, in the current situation, in the unfolding war of extermination in Gaza, Tekeya are working as the only source of food, without a proper secondary system to receive the saved ones. This results in more pressure on existing Tekeyas being exhorted. Further, Tekeyas currently depend on donations and humanitarian food aid. Both are sourced from outside Gaza. Even worse, Tekeya's facilities have been targeted and bombed by "Israeli" forces.

The National reported in January 2024 (The National, 2024) that "Gaza's charity kitchens struggle with dwindling supplies and rising costs". Even worse, the restriction and banning on Gazan's ability to receive donations from outside have dried the resources feeding the Tekeyas to operate. On March 2024, Aljazeera reported from North Gaza that the sight of Tekeyas providing food to groups of the hungry population has become rare after it was held about 3 months ago daily in most shelter centres and many regions and neighbourhoods (Aljazeera, 2024t), and then AlQuds (2024) reported that Dozens of charitable Takeya's stopped working due to the "Israeli" systematic starvation policies. Migdad and Buheji (2024) mentioned the critical role of Tekeya in compensating for the loophole on the internal front.

4.1.2. Persistent Survival Despite Adversity

There are many causes for food scarcity. One of which is the Palestinians of Gaza have been forced out of their homes that generally have the food, food ingredients and tools to make food. This sudden displacement with short notice as short as zero minutes sometimes, resulted in almost all Gazans leaving their homes without essential belongings such as money, gold and precious items that can be used as money to buy food and tools.

The other cause is the lack of transport vehicles to transfer their food, tools, and essential belongings due to fuel deprivation and bombing of their vehicles. The attacks and thefts on the displacement unsafe corridors were declared safe by “Israelis” and violated by them, too. Deprivation of water, bombing, burning and destroying crops and agricultural areas by the “Israeli army” using air forces, land shells and even tree bulldozers, as the ones filmed and reported, documented how Gaza lost 90% of its olive trees. QudsPress (2024a)

The Israeli Defence Forces (IDF) army prevented food aid trucks from entering Gaza since the beginning of the War on October 7th, 2023. best scenario minimising the number that can enter and restricting their movement inside Gaza to ensure that certain areas remain with no food aid. The focused IDF attacks on food aid trucks and intentional delays in the entry of the material also spoiled the food to maximise the suffering of Gazans. This was combined with the IDF, which consisted of targeted destruction of bakeries and food preparation places. Even the food aid, which was meant to help eliminate famines and was suitable for babies and young children, was bombed. Hassoun et al. (2024)

“The Israeli” air force bombed and shot fishers' boats and individuals when attempting to fish in the sea. The IDF even dared to bomb trucks of food aid and kill volunteers and staff from the World Central Kitchen (WCK) vehicles, resulting in the murder of seven of their workers (from Australia, Palestine, Poland and the United Kingdom) on April 1st, 2024 (Aljazeera, 2024a). They even extended their targeting and bombing to food stores and distribution centres that were permitted to enter Gaza.

To create further chaos the IDF targeted and killed police forces responsible for maintaining the order and management of fair distribution of food aid, resulting in armed gangs stealing most of the food aid that was allowed to enter Gaza. Not only that, they started bombing takeya's, making and distributing food to displaced families.

4.1.3 Diversifying the Means for Survival

Gazans naturally started trading goods in the market to diversify their means of survival, exchanging what they found in the aid package for what was essential for their survival. Some Gazans started growing vegetables and fruits at displacement locations, between tents (Bisan from Gaza, 2024). For example, in Jabalia – North Gaza, Mohammad Qomssan was featured by The Guardian (2024), starting a plantation, a small garden in the middle of the rubble, to grow vegetables using an old bathtub, plastic buckets, a tin can and other containers of all shapes and sizes found around.

Mohammad mentioned the famine and severe malnutrition Gazans live in, explaining the destruction of farming lands and scarcity of vegetables in the North Gaza market; he started his initiative with some seeds he was able to find. Al-Qomssan family's house was destroyed by “Israeli” forces, like other houses in North Gaza. Still, Mohammad and his family decided to re-root themselves in their land, clearing out some of the rubble and creating a temporary living space by extending a tarpaulin sheet and starting their little project to find something to eat.

More initiatives are expected from such a group of young people who would strive to grow all sorts of vegetables and fruits and then distribute them to refugee camps to be planted in their neighbourhood.

Starting new locations for “Tekeya” replacement and forming groups to distribute food packages to refugee camps such as Malak Fada (MalakFada2003) and Islam Ayoub and Samid Zourob (NewArab, 2024). Ayoub and Zourob, as well as other young people in Gaza, started initiatives to receive displaced Palestinians and provide them with food, shelter, and basic needs. They set up different groups of volunteers to provide tents, cook food, check for refugees needing urgent medical attention, and try to ease their suffering. Malak Fada, in addition to cooking and distributing food packages, visits children in different places, talks to them, cheers them up and helps them. She refers to herself as a humanitarian activist from Gaza, and she established Malak Fund to feed the Gazans.

When Palestinians were forcefully displaced to Rafah, they were met with welcome and warm meals from residents of Rafah. Malak is one of them. Children in Rafah know and love her as it appears in different videos when they see her, and apparently, they follow her social media account and think of her as an “angel”. The details of cooking, packaging and the messages Malak sent through her videos are another level of care, respect and support. What Malak and other social media heroes in the Gaza Strip provide for children and young people is much more than food or help; they provide inspiration and hope. Buheji (2024a)

Being aware of the hardship of displacement and what displaced Palestinians faced from the occupation forces on their way from their homes to Rafah, individuals and groups of refugees in Rafah started receiving new ones. They received them with welcoming words, and they shared what they had of little food and water with them. This initiative provided life-saving water and a bit of food for survivors of the forced displacement with all sorts of assaults and violations of human rights, including walking barefoot and losing children and family members on the way. Collective awareness and communal unity play a part in survival in these devastating situations. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023a)

Families were selling or trading food or staff for milk and essentials. Examples were seen in dozens of videos of children filmed selling small bites. When asked why, the answer was always related to supporting younger siblings or the family. Young people formed community groups to screen and check on families and provide food whenever available, replacing the role of police and formal order official organisations.

Small-scale food producers (SSFP) initiative of “recycling seedlings”. They took the initiative to start farming after returning to North Gaza to find their homes turned to rubble but then found hope in noticing some plants growing in between the ruins. Yousef Saqr Abu Rabee’, a 24-year-old agricultural engineer, returned to northern Gaza in March 2024 to find that the occupation had demolished his blossoming farmland. Going out to find anything to eat in North Gaza has been extremely risky and has had little outcome, if any.

The idea started when Eng. Abu Rabee came across little plants grown from pepper and eggplant pods falling into the soil and watered by rain. His positive problem-solving orientation led him to assume that this could lead to a resolution for the existing famine dilemma. Using his agricultural engineering skills and knowledge and a rational problem-solving style, he decided to create an incubator and collect all the tiny seedlings he could find.

Many problems and obstacles existed, such as the scarcity of water and the lack of fuel to operate irrigation motors, the absence of good agricultural natural nutrients-rich soil that both has been destroyed and polluted by the occupation bulldozing and bombardments using EWIPA, white phosphorus and other unknown pollutants for more than a year all over Gaza, and inflicting irreversible damage to soil and water and agricultural lands, especially the olive trees and other deeply rooted trees, Buheji and Al-Muhannadi (2023). This could be a dead end for any hope of planting in Gaza, as expressed by experts and officials focusing on the obstacles. However, he thought of problems in different ways. The first problem was solved temporarily using plastic containers found in the rubble till suitable land was found, and the second problem was solved by trying to make “artificial soil”. Following a methodological logical problem-solving style, he collected soil produced from tree trash that had been processed to make it fit for agricultural use after travelling to different locations across North Gaza to acquire this artificial soil.

The young engineer then involved family and neighbours in finding more seeds, a positive step that got eight more types of seeds, including pumpkin, to start his incubator nursery. He then took the hard decision to publicise the initiative in the hope of receiving support that could allow the project to grow and feed more people who have nothing at all in North Gaza with the siege and destruction. His initiative started to show success, and he managed to feed people in North Gaza with his production, and he started receiving support from inside and outside Gaza. In his social media account, “Diary of a Farmer”, he published pictures of children helping him plant seeds and learning from him. It took the occupation a few days to shell his project.

The young Palestinian hero who survived the attack declared that he would continue planting edible plants to feed the starving people despite all risks, and he called upon FAO and other relevant UN organisations to support the initiative. He was featured on many news fronts from all over the world. Scholars from Al-Azhar University in Egypt confirmed that with support, this initiative could provide essential food for Gaza’s citizens, like the successful initiative in the US during World War I, resulting in the planting of about 18 million gardens, but only with proper support. “Victory Gardens” in Ukraine is another recent example. FAO (2021), SkiDevNet (2024), Aljazeera (2024d), Haaretz News (2024).

The risks are incredibly high with the occupation forces targeting every hope for life in Gaza, but Eng. Abu Rabee’ has indeed planted not only seeds for edible plants but also for hope and inspiration at an extreme time of adversity. His idea and dream are to encourage everyone to plant it in their houses, on rooftops, on the rubble, and everywhere in Gaza. Yousef’s goal is to establish self-sufficiency in the food sector, which needs rejuvenation by all citizens, and not just specialised farmers. Unfortunately, like many beautiful dreams and heroes in Gaza, before publishing the paper, the young Gazan engineer was targeted and killed after several unsuccessful attempts to assassinate him.

4.2. Water scarcity

4.2.1 Background

On October 8th, 2023, the occupation authority announced that they would deprive Gaza of water, food and energy, and they did. Surface water sources were either buried by cement or became a hazardous place to visit with the death penalty by the Israeli army. Existing water desalination and purification plants were either destroyed or difunctional due to an embargo on spare parts for maintenance of completion years ago.

Water was available in Rafah from Egypt for some time, but then it stopped, and since the second quarter of 2024, “Israel” occupied Rafah as well as the borders with Egypt and the crossing. The North suffered the most especially for those refusing to leave their cities and forced South. People ended up drinking from any available water, bottles coming with the little aid trucks allowed to reach them, or let it be dirty, contaminated water from any source. A mother was filmed collecting drops of condensed water from a truck in a tiny plastic container and giving it to her child.

4.2.2 Persistent Survival Despite Adversity

Displaced Palestinian lady engineer Enas Al-Ghoul invented a desalination and purifying water system in Khan Younis that she named a solar evaporator, and her story was known in August 2024, Aljazeera (2024b & 2024c). The system works on solar power to turn seawater into drinkable water. The evaporator uses a wooden box closed with glass and leather, known as a solar still. The box contains holes for water to enter and exit, where before leaving the water passes through a layer of activated charcoal to purify it. A solar still is a device that uses solar energy to distil water, to produce pure water from polluted or salty water by heating the water using solar energy, which leads to the evaporation of the water and then the vapor condenses to return to the liquid state in the form of pure water. Buheji and Al-Muhannadi (2023)

4.2.3 Diversifying the Means for Survival

Enas positive problem-solving orientation (PPO) directed her to consider using what is available to solve an existing problem for her and many others. Amid scarcity in everything due to the tight siege preventing essentials from entering Gaza and reaching the people. She created this device using simple tools like wood, glass, and leather. Her logic is that citizens in the Gaza Strip suffer from water scarcity and are close to the seashore, but there are no other reliable methods. She has engineering knowledge, techniques and skills that can be used to invent a distillation system that can answer current needs, at least in light of the water crisis that the population is suffering from, making a PSP, reflecting her capabilities of sensible, thoughtful, and systematic application of practical problem-solving skills, or rational problem-solving style that is most likely to result in positive outcomes. Aburezeq and Kasik (2021 & 2022).

On a small scale, a gentleman from Jabalia camp in North Gaza in June 2024 created a simple small-scale device to purify and desalinate seawater as they had no water to drink. He utilised his knowledge that rocks, sands, coals, and cotton can purify water. Using an empty plastic water bottle, he filled it with layers of all of them, added the seawater on top, made a hole in the lid, and got his drinkable water. If he considered the possible pollution, or the bad quality of the output water, he probably wouldn't have attempted it and maybe died or got sick of thirst and dehydration. However, the positive problem-solving orientation enabled him to save his life and maybe the lives of other citizens in North Gaza.

4.3. Teaching planting trees and surviving genocide

4.3.1 *Persistent Survival Despite Adversity*

Mehdi and his “Cool” initiative or “Cool Rozela Flowers” Initiative has accounts on Instagram, Facebook, TikTok and YouTube, and always starts with a warm “Hala Belquawali” that means “Hello the dearests” with a big smile and beautiful calm, cheerful voice. We sometimes thought we were mistaken and that he was a Palestinian agricultural professor living in another country, especially with the dozens of videos teaching how to grow and care for trees with the utmost professionalism, focus and joy. It is only when he mentions “our refugee camp” or “here in Gaza” or when he shows the surroundings or people around that we are sure that he is Gazan himself and living under genocide. His case study is unique for this reason, among other reasons illustrated in this section. Rozelaflowers (2024), Coolrozelaflowers (2024).

4.3.2 *Diversifying the Means for Survival*

Florists of “Cool Rozella Flowers” led many initiatives for the Palestinian citizens forced out of their homes and towns, such as "vegetable baskets", "lightening the camp", "milk and kits for children", and “Zait w Za'tar”. However, his special initiatives that show a great sense of positive orientation towards problem-solving are food production teaching and focusing on children’s mental health. The Florist has been planting edible vegetables and fruits in the refugee camps, caring for them daily and teaching others how to grow every plant.

This initiative was further supported by short videos showing how to plant onions, foles, and even apples in straightforward ways. His YouTube channel teaches in detail how to plant a tree and deal with issues encountered in the process. Seven professional videos explain how to plant each fruit and flower step by step. A video demonstrates how to grow a mango from its seed in the kitchen, starting with options for extracting the embryo, how much water is used in each stage to follow, till transferring it to soil in a pot within weeks, and when to plant it in soil and how to accelerate the wait time needed for production CoolRoselaFlowers (2023).

Similar details are given for pineapple, cucumbers, and avocado, and names based on the high fertility of Palestinian soil. He turned his agricultural skills into a data bank for everyone to learn from and apply, whether they came to him to know or virtually through his Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube accounts.

Mehdi presents everything with a calm smile and words of hope and encouragement. Plants face many problems, such as broken branches or parasite attacks. He made unique videos to address each. In one of his videos, he turned dry or broken branches into opportunities for better production, RozelaFolowers (2024b).

Gaza’s Florist has sessions to teach children about planting vegetables, giving them time to learn with fun and joy in collaboration with other initiatives, and building a playground for the children of refugee camps in Gaza. Two months ago, an excellent school celebrated the graduation of 120 children from a school term, teaching them the complete Palestinian curriculum. This was achieved in a tiny classroom in a tent, RozelaFlowers, (2024sc). The students were from 4 different levels, including kindergarten and intermediate- each group having their own classes, curriculum, programs and evaluation before graduation. Graduating from a term or semester amid a genocidal war that can target and burn alive children at any second is a unique and outstanding achievement, made possible with dedicated teachers and aware parents and children eager to learn and restore some aspects of their lives.

The summary of Cool's initiative is enjoying the day and making the best while preparing for the future by planting and caring for the plants. This was applied in literal, figurative, or metaphorical meaning in "Cool Rozela" initiatives.

In his home, he had a fantastic plantation that he left when he was forcefully displaced from his home and town. In one of his videos, he showed the farm he created in the new home with some stuff recycled from his old house, which indicates that his home was destroyed. In his refugee camp, although everyone knows that it is only a temporary camp till the occupation decides to bomb them and force them to run for their lives away from everything, they created to make life a bit easier, he created a new garden and a new heaven for his children and people around him. Every member of his family is participating and having joy and fun with him. His kids participate in growing trees and caring for them, filming and documenting the initiatives and running the social media. His elderly mother's initiative at the beginning of winter was to make wool hats, "Tawaqi", for as many children in the camp as possible to help warm them in the winter. He took one of them and started wearing it in his following episodes, RozelaFlowers (2024h). In one of his videos, he said that today, we live full of love and laughter, surrounded by the people we love and making everyone happy. This possibly explains his positive attitude, beautiful smile, and relaxed style in everything he says and does. He cannot control what the enemies of life will do, but he can control how he, as a florist full of love for life, spends each valuable hour of his day and how he impacts the lives of others, even those living far away from him, through social media. The first author of this paper has been teaching children in Bahrain and other countries in the MENA Region how to plant their own food by their hands, and she considers his videos to be the best references, especially for children in the Levant.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aljazeera (2024a). What is World Central Kitchen, whose team was attacked by Israel in Gaza?. What is World Central Kitchen, whose team was attacked by Israel in Gaza? | Israel-Palestine conflict News | Al Jazeera (April 2nd 2024)
- [2] Aljazeera (2024b): An engineer in Gaza invents a system for desalinating sea water. 8/8/2024. <https://www.aljazeera.net/tech/2024/8/8/%D9%85%D9%87%D9%86%D8%AF%D8%B3%D8%A9-%D8%A8%D8%BA%D8%B2%D8%A9-%D8%AA%D8%A8%D8%AA%D9%83%D8%B1-%D9%86%D8%B8%D8%A7%D9%85%D8%A7-%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%AD%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%A1#:~:text=%D8%AA%D9%85%D9%83%D9%86%D8%AA%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%87%D9%86%D8%AF%D8%B3%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%81%D9%84%D8%B3%D8%B7%D9%8A%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%86%D8%A7%D8%B2%D8%AD%D8%A9%20%D8%A5%D9%8A%D9%86%D8%A7%D8%B3,%D9%85%D9%86%20%D8%A3%D9%83%D8%AA%D9%88%D8%A8%D8%B1%2F%D8%AA%D8%B4%D8%B1%D9%8A%D9%86%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D9%88%D9%84%202023.>
- [3] Aljazeera (2024c). Personal initiative for desalinating seawater. June 1st 2024. https://www.google.com/search?q=%D8%BA%D8%B2%D8%A9+%D8%B4%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%A8+%D8%AA%D8%AD%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A9+%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%A1+%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A8%D8%AD%D8%B1+%D8%AC%D9%87%D8%A7%D8%B2+%D8%A7%D8%AE%D8%AA%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%B9&sca_esv=46d1524bbf4d7360&xsrf=ADLYWII8J9Moqh6yLVEqiWt44AE3O5afpA%3A1731722922460&ei=qv43Z-3iG4iLxc8Phe_oyQ8&ved=0ahUKEwj35HN4t-JAxWIRfEDHYU3OvkQ4dUDCA8&uact=5&eq=%D8%BA%D8%B2%D8%A9+%D8%B4

Surviving Despite Intentional Food & Water Scarcity – Cases of Resilience from Gaza (2023-2024)

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- [4] Aljazeera (2024d). “Plant on top of the rubble” an initiative by a young Palestinian to save the northern Gaza Strip from hunger. 5/4/2024.
<https://www.aljazeera.net/lifestyle/2024/4/5/%D8%A7%D8%B2%D8%B1%D8%B9%D9%88%D8%A7-%D9%81%D9%88%D9%82-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B1%D9%83%D8%A7%D9%85-%D9%85%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AF%D8%B1%D8%A9-%D8%B4%D8%A7%D8%A8-%D9%81%D9%84%D8%B3%D8%B7%D9%8A%D9%86%D9%8A>
- [5] Al-Muhannadi, K and Buheji, M (2024) Value-Based Resilience Stories from Gaza (During War 2023), International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(1), pp. 15-37.
- [6] AlQuds (2024). Gaza: Dozens of charitable hospices stopped working due to the Israeli starvation policy. 18 November 2024. <https://www.alquds.co.uk/%D8%BA%D8%B2%D8%A9-%D8%AA%D9%88%D9%82%D9%81-%D8%B9%D8%B4%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D9%83%D8%A7%D9%8A%D8%A7-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AE%D9%8A%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%B9%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D9%85/>
- [7] Bisan From Gaza. Palestinians In Displacement Camps are Planting Fruits and Vegetables to Try to Feed Their Families. 19 June 2024. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GhMj_cEGp5M
- [8] Buheji, M (2024a) Streams of Inspiration from Gaza Despite Genocide, Reflections from 2023/2024 War), International Journal of Inspiration & Resilience Economy, Vol. 8 (2), pp. 57-64.
- [9] Buheji, M (2024b) Avoiding Resilience Fatigue- Navigating ‘Collective Pain’ and ‘Collective Happiness’ in Gaza (War of 2023/2024), International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences 2024, 14(1): 22-33.
- [10] Buheji, M; Al-Muhannadi, K (2023) Mitigating Risks of Environmental Impacts on Gaza - Review of Precautions & Solutions post (2023 War), International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology, 14(7), pp. 15-47.
- [11] Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2023a) Raising Gaza Survival Capacity as Per Violence Experienced, Lesson from Best War Survival Stories in Recent History, International Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJARSSH), 7 (1), 2023, pp. 22–48.
- [12] Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2023b) “Gaza” – Towards an Agile Resilience, International Journal of Management (IJM), 14(7), pp. 120- 136.
- [13] Cool Rozela Flowers (2023). Growing mango from seed. <https://youtu.be/mROw5erfUKk?si=WJgpUJsMHZ0JYWo>
- [14] Cool Rozela flowers (2024).
<https://www.youtube.com/c/COOLRozelaFlowers/videos>
- [15] Cool Rozela Flowers (2024f). Planting Fool.

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SoSRBH-L674>
- [16] FAO (2021). Defining and identifying Small-scale food producers to monitor indicators 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 Aida Khalil Statistician, Office of Chief Statistician (FAO): Regional Training for Africa. Virtual Training on SDG Indicators 2.3.1 and 2.3.2. 11-14 October 2021.
- [17] <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b16733b2-1670-41b6-93db-565b0087cfde/content>
- [18] Haaretz News (2024). Gaza's Strawberry Harvest, Once a Symbol of Abundance, Is Another Victim of the War. 28 March 2024. <https://www.haaretz.com/middle-east-news/palestinians/2024-03-28/ty-article/.premium/gazas-strawberry-harvest-once-a-symbol-of-abundance-is-another-victim-of-the-war/0000018e-857c-d0d3-a98e-d7ffc2940000>
- [19] Hassoun A, Al-Muhannadi K, Hassan HF, Hamad A, Khwaldia K, Buheji M and Al Jawaldeh A (2024) From acute food insecurity to famine: how the 2023/2024 war on Gaza has dramatically set back sustainable development goal 2 to end hunger. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 8:1402150.
- [20] Reliefweb (2024r). Islamic Relief condemns attack at Gaza school where it distributes food. 10 August 2024. <https://reliefweb.int/report/occupied-palestinian-territory/islamic-relief-condemns-attack-gaza-school-where-it-distributes-food>
- [21] SkiDevNet (2024). Seeds sown among Gaza rubble offer hope of food. 8 May 2024. <https://www.scidev.net/global/news/seeds-sown-among-gaza-rubble-offer-hope-of-food/>
- [22] The Guardian (2024). The gardener of Gaza: sowing hope by growing vegetables amid the rubble. September 2024. <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/article/2024/aug/28/the-gardener-of-gaza-sowing-hope-by-growing-vegetables-amid-the-rubble>

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